

Harmony and Discord: Navigating the Diagnostic Challenge of Atypical Spitzoid Melanocytic Nevus Resembling Melanoma

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1. ABSTRACT

Spitz nevi, although benign, can present histological features that closely mimic melanoma, especially when they display atypical characteristics. Differentiating Spitz nevi from Spitzoid melanomas remains challenging due to overlapping histological features and complex pathological classifications. This case report aims to illustrate the diagnostic complexities associated with distinguishing between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas and to emphasize the importance of comprehensive evaluation and multidisciplinary collaboration in achieving an accurate diagnosis.

Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas share similar histological features, including spindled and/or epithelioid nevocyanocytes. Key distinguishing features of Spitzoid melanomas include larger, irregular nests with dyscohesion among melanocytes and epidermal atrophy, in contrast to the typical hyperplasia seen in Spitz nevi. The invasive dermal component of Spitzoid melanomas, resembling Atypical Spitz Tumor (AST), poses additional diagnostic challenges. Accurate differentiation between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas is crucial due to the significantly different management and surveillance strategies.

We present a case with a pigmented lesion on her thigh, initially diagnosed as a highly atypical compound melanocytic proliferation with positive margins. Multidisciplinary consultation, advanced imaging, and a second pathology review clarified the diagnosis as an atypical Spitzoid nevus rather than melanoma. This definitive diagnosis informed a focused management strategy, including wide-margin re-excision to ensure complete removal and ongoing surveillance instead of more aggressive oncologic interventions. This case highlights the need for

thorough histopathological evaluation and multidisciplinary collaboration to navigate the diagnostic uncertainties and ensure appropriate patient management.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Overview of Spitz Nevi and Spitzoid Melanomas

Spitz nevi, often encountered in dermatological practice, are benign melanocytic lesions that typically present as pink, dome-shaped nodules. Though benign, their histological features can closely resemble those of malignant melanoma, particularly when atypical characteristics are present. Spitz nevi predominantly feature spindled and/or epithelioid nevocyanocytes, which can lead to significant diagnostic challenges. The dilemma arises because these lesions can exhibit similar features to those found in melanoma, making differentiation critical yet complex [1].

Spitzoid Melanomas represent a more serious diagnostic concern. These lesions can be particularly problematic due to their spindled and/or epithelioid melanocytic morphology, which overlaps with that of Spitz nevi. Histologically, Spitzoid melanomas are distinguished by several key features. The junctional component of Spitzoid melanoma typically presents as larger and irregular nests of melanocytes with scattered pagetoid features. Additionally, epidermal atrophy, in contrast to the hyperplasia observed in Spitz nevi, is a distinguishing feature. Dyscohesion among melanocytes within these nests—rather than the clefting often seen around Spitz nests—serves as another critical differentiator [2].

The invasive dermal component of Spitzoid melanomas bears resemblance to Atypical Spitz Tumor (AST), characterized by large nodules with a compact, sheet-like growth pattern, cytologic atypia, and inadequate maturation of melanocytes into the dermis. The presence of these atypical features underscores the diagnostic complexity associated with these lesions. Accurate identification is paramount because Spitzoid melanomas require a more aggressive management strategy compared to Spitz nevi.

2.2. Challenges in Diagnosis

The diagnostic challenges associated with Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas are rooted in their overlapping histological features. Spitzoid lesions—whether benign or malignant—can present with a spectrum of atypical features that complicate the diagnostic process. Historically, Spitz nevi were mistakenly classified as juvenile melanomas, a misconception that has evolved with advances in understanding their true nature. Modern diagnostic approaches rely heavily on detailed histopathological evaluations, complemented by immunophenotypic and molecular analyses to differentiate these lesions effectively.

Recent advancements in immunophenotypic and molecular analyses have provided valuable insights into the biological behaviour of these lesions, offering more refined diagnostic criteria. Despite these advances, distinguishing between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas remains challenging due to their histological similarities and the nuanced presentation of atypical features. This complexity is further compounded by the potential for

overlap between benign and malignant characteristics, making accurate diagnosis critical for appropriate management.

2.3. Case Significance

The significance of this case lies in its illustration of the diagnostic difficulties inherent in differentiating between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas. The patient's presentation—a highly atypical Spitzoid nevus with features suggestive of malignancy—necessitated a thorough investigation involving multidisciplinary consultations and advanced imaging techniques. This case highlights the importance of a comprehensive diagnostic approach, including re-excision and detailed histopathological review, to achieve an accurate diagnosis and inform management decisions.

The management strategies for malignant melanoma and Spitzoid nevi differ significantly. Melanoma requires aggressive treatment and close surveillance due to its potential for metastasis, whereas Spitz nevi, despite their atypical features, typically warrant a less aggressive approach. The case underscores the need for vigilance in monitoring for potential malignant transformation and emphasizes the role of a multidisciplinary team in navigating these complex diagnostic scenarios.

3. CASE PRESENTATION

3.1. Initial Presentation

A 44-year-old female with a history of tobacco use presented for evaluation of a pigmented lesion on her right thigh. The patient reported noticing the lesion several months earlier, describing changes in color and texture that prompted her to seek medical attention. The lesion had been initially removed at a local family clinic, where histopathological analysis revealed highly atypical findings, leading to a referral for further evaluation (Figure 1 to 3).

Figure 1: Asymmetrical compound melanocytic proliferation well-circumscribed on the one edge of the lesion present for evaluation.

Figure 2: Fascicles/nests of melanocytes with spindle/epithelioid differential and focal pagetoid intraepidermal involvement without consumption of the epidermis. There is also a vague suggestion of maturation within dermal melanocytes with smaller nested and individual melanocytes in deeper portions of the lesion.

Figure 3: Nested and individual melanocytes with epithelioid cytology and conspicuous nucleoli.

3.2. DIAGNOSTIC WORKUP

3.2.1. Initial Biopsy: The biopsy demonstrated a highly atypical compound melanocytic proliferation characterized by epithelioid (Spitzoid) melanocytic differentiation and a brisk lymphocytic infiltrate. Positive margins on the initial excision raised concerns for incomplete removal and possible malignancy.

3.3. Multidisciplinary Consultation

Given the atypical nature of the lesion, the patient was referred to a dermatologist specializing in melanoma and skin cancers. A re-excision with wide margins was recommended to ensure complete removal and accurate histopathological assessment. The case was further reviewed by a tumor board and a panel of pathologists. Despite extensive analysis, melanoma could not be definitively ruled out, prompting additional diagnostic steps.

3.3.1. Imaging Studies

- **MRI of the Lower Extremity:** Revealed bilateral inguinal lymphadenopathy, with the largest node on the right measuring 1.2 cm × 2.5 cm and the largest on the left measuring 0.8 cm × 2.2 cm.
- **PET Scan:** Showed no FDG (fluorodeoxyglucose) activity in the inguinal lymph nodes, lowering suspicion for active metastatic disease.

3.3.2. Second Pathology Review

A second opinion from an academic dermatopathology center concluded that the lesion was an atypical Spitzoid nevus rather than melanoma. The immunophenotypic profile and histological findings supported this diagnosis.

4. MANAGEMENT

4.1. Surgical Intervention

The patient underwent a re-excision with a 1 cm margin, ensuring complete removal of any residual atypical cells. Histopathological analysis of the re-excision specimen confirmed the diagnosis of an atypical Spitzoid nevus with clear margins.

4.2. Follow-Up and Surveillance

Post-re-excision, the patient was placed under close dermatological surveillance. Follow-up included regular skin evaluations to monitor for recurrence or new lesions. Imaging findings of bilateral lymphadenopathy, despite no metabolic activity, warranted ongoing vigilance. The patient was counselled on recognizing signs of recurrence or malignancy and advised to report any changes promptly.

4.3. Summary of Diagnostic Process and Outcome

The patient initially presented with a pigmented lesion on her thigh, initially diagnosed as a highly atypical compound melanocytic proliferation with positive margins. Multidisciplinary consultation, advanced imaging, and a second pathology review clarified the diagnosis as an atypical Spitzoid nevus rather than melanoma. This definitive diagnosis informed a focused management strategy, including wide-margin re-excision to ensure complete removal and ongoing surveillance instead of more aggressive oncologic interventions. The patient remains under regular dermatological follow-up, with no evidence of recurrence or malignancy to date.

Table 1: Differences in Spitz Nevi, atypical spitz tumors and spitzoid melanomas

Feature	Spitz Nevi	Atypical Spitz Tumors	Spitzoid Melanomas
Clinical Presentation	Symmetrical, pink or pigmented dome-shaped lesion	Larger, irregular borders, mixed pigmentation	Asymmetric, irregular pigmentation, nodular
Histological Features	Symmetry, maturation towards the base, minimal atypia	Focal atypia, asymmetry, incomplete maturation	Severe atypia, mitotic figures, asymmetry
Mitotic Activity	Rare	Increased but localized	High, often deep and atypical
Growth Pattern	Well-circumscribed, limited to epidermis	Epidermal and dermal involvement, possible mitotic spread	Vertical growth, dermal invasion, potential for metastasis
Prognosis	Benign	Intermediate; unclear malignant potential	High risk of metastasis and recurrence

5. DISCUSSION

Spitz nevi are benign melanocytic lesions commonly observed in children and young adults, characterized by their distinctive appearance and histological features. These lesions typically present as round, pink or reddish bumps, though they may vary in color and texture. They account for a relatively small proportion of surgically removed moles, roughly 1% of total mole removals. In contrast, Spitzoid melanomas, while sharing some morphological similarities with Spitz nevi, are malignant and present a significant diagnostic challenge due to their overlapping features [1].

Distinguishing between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas is critical yet challenging due to the similarities in their histopathological characteristics. Spitz nevi are characterized by spindled and/or epithelioid nevocyanocytes, and the lesions generally demonstrate a symmetrical architecture with well-circumscribed borders. Histologically, Spitz nevi typically exhibit a uniform growth pattern with minimal cytological atypia and a lack of invasive behaviour. In contrast, Spitzoid melanomas often present with more irregular, larger nests of melanocytes that demonstrate significant dyscohesion and atypical features [2].

Recent advances in immunophenotypic and molecular analyses have improved our understanding of these lesions. Spitz nevi are often marked by the presence of spindled or epithelioid melanocytes without the irregular nests seen in malignant counterparts. Molecular analyses have shown that Spitz nevi typically do not possess the genetic mutations associated with melanoma, further supporting their benign nature.

Conversely, Spitzoid melanomas display larger and more irregular nests of melanocytes, often with scattered pagetoid cells (melanocytes within the epidermis). These lesions are also associated with epidermal atrophy rather than hyperplasia and exhibit dyscohesion among melanocytes within the nests. This dyscohesion, combined with the presence of atypical mitotic figures and a more diffuse infiltrative growth pattern, differentiates them from Spitz nevi.

Historically, Spitz nevi were often misclassified as juvenile melanomas due to their similar histological appearance and aggressive growth patterns. This misconception was primarily due to the challenge in differentiating between these lesions based on histopathology alone, differences shown in [Table 1](#). However, improved understanding of the genetic and immunohistochemical profiles of these lesions has clarified their distinct nature. Spitz nevi are now recognized as benign entities with a generally favourable prognosis, whereas Spitzoid melanomas, including those resembling Atypical Spitz Tumor (AST), are recognized for their potential malignancy and variable clinical behaviour [\[3,4\]](#).

The diagnostic process for atypical Spitzoid lesions requires a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach involving dermatologists, pathologists, and oncologists. Histopathological assessments, while crucial, are not always definitive. The complexity of differentiating between Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas underscores the necessity of advanced diagnostic tools and a collaborative approach. Multidisciplinary tumor boards and consultations with expert dermatopathologists play a *vital* role in achieving an accurate diagnosis and determining the appropriate management strategy.

The challenge in differentiating these lesions is compounded by the potential for atypical features in both Spitz nevi and Spitzoid melanomas. For example, the presence of atypical lymphocytic infiltrates, as observed in the presented case, adds another layer of complexity. The decision to pursue further imaging or additional surgical intervention often hinges on these subtle differences, with potential implications for patient management and prognosis [\[2\]](#).

The clinical implications of diagnostic uncertainty in cases of atypical Spitzoid lesions are significant. As demonstrated by the presented case, imaging findings of bilateral inguinal lymphadenopathy, despite negative FDG activity on PET scans, highlight the importance of vigilant monitoring. The presence of lymphadenopathy, even in the absence of active metabolic disease, necessitates ongoing surveillance due to the potential for metastatic involvement [\[4\]](#).

Management strategies for atypical Spitzoid lesions must balance the need for thorough investigation with the risk of overtreatment. The presented case exemplifies the need for a nuanced approach, involving wide excision and careful follow-up, while avoiding unnecessary interventions. This balance is crucial to minimize patient morbidity and ensure timely detection of any potential malignancy.

6. CONCLUSION

The ongoing challenges in distinguishing Spitz nevi from Spitzoid melanomas highlight the importance of continued research and refinement in diagnostic practices. Advances in immunophenotypic and molecular analyses have provided valuable insights into the nature of these lesions, but the need for a multidisciplinary approach remains

paramount. This case report underscores the complexities associated with atypical Spitzoid lesions and emphasizes the importance of comprehensive evaluations and collaborative efforts in managing these challenging cases. By raising awareness among oncologists and dermatologists, we hope to improve diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes in the face of these diagnostic challenges.

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